

Large Language Models As Standardization Tools: A Case Study Of Automatically Standardizing Transportation Data

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Abstract

The standardization of transportation data into uniform formats, such as the General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS), is crucial for ensuring interoperability, data quality, and effective decision making within the transport sector. This paper explores the innovative application of Large Language Models (LLMs) and Vision Language Models (VLMs), in automating the transformation of unstandardized data, including text and images, into standardized formats. Using the advanced reasoning capabilities of these models, we propose a methodology for extracting and standardizing transportation and mobility datasets. The focus of the work is in demonstrating the potential of LLMs in handling domain-specific standardization challenges. The paper details the development of a pipeline, from data collection and structured-data generation to the integration of human-in-the-loop to enhance model performance. On a set of 50 real-world timetable images, the best model, gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06, achieved mean±st.dev. GTFS-table scores of 4.78±0.58 (stops), 4.55±0.75 (trips) and 3.96±0.96 (stop_times) on a 1–5 scale.

Keywords: data engineering, generative AI, LLMs, VLMs, transportation engineering, data standardization, prompt engineering, human-in-the-loop.

1. Introduction

1.1 Problem Statement

Data standards are considered vital in the transport domain because they ensure consistent, reliable data exchange and system interoperability among operators, regulators, and service providers. Standardized data also supports high-quality analytics, enabling planners to understand trends, optimize infrastructure and traffic management, and allocate resources effectively. Moreover, adherence to standards enhances safety, compliance, and process monitoring. Transforming unstructured into structured data is a core data-engineering task, supported by numerous tools for cleaning and processing. However, converting structured data into a specific standard is more challenging and domain-dependent, requiring deep technical knowledge of each element's meaning, inter-element references, and correct data types. Learning these nuances is time-consuming, which makes custom software with an intuitive interface for importing or generating data and automating its

mapping to the target standard extremely valuable. Building such software demands careful API design, data modeling, validation, and precise mapping to the chosen standard's elements.

This work investigates the potential of modern generative AI, similarly to how they were surveyed by (Chang et al. 2024), which have capabilities of text and image understanding and text generation to attempt to automate the production of cleaned structured data in a predetermined format and thus bypass the need for custom software or at least enhance their capabilities. The study concentrates on the transportation domain, specifically on extracting GTFS tables from free text descriptions or a single image of an operator's network. We validate the automatic pipeline methods using: 1. Custom scoring methods via the LLM-as-a-judge approach, 2. the proprietary platform TransiTool (TransiTool, 2024), which is a data management platform for transport operators to, among other functionalities, standardize their data into GTFS, NeTEx and other data standards.

Research Question Explored: Can LLMs convert transportation images into GTFS with high fidelity?
Contribution: An end-to-end pipeline that automatically generates GTFS tables from image or raw text transportation schedules.

1.2 Data Standards In Transportation

General Transit Feed Specification (GTFS) is a prominent data standard used in public transportation. GTFS establishes a universal framework for organizing public transit schedules and relevant geographic data. This framework allows transit authorities to disseminate their information in a format readily compatible with various applications, including Google Maps (General Transit Feed Specification, 2024). Consequently, users gain seamless access to transit details like schedules, routes, and fares, facilitated by this universally adopted open-access data standard. GTFS standard aims to improve the accessibility and interoperability of transit data, enhancing the efficiency and user experience of public transportation systems globally. GTFS includes several required tables, in the form of .txt files, essential for representing public transit systems. These include:

agency: Details the transit agencies, **stops:** Lists all stops and stations, **routes:** Defines the routes available, **trips:** Specifies individual trips along routes, **stop_times:** Shows arrival and departure times at each stop per trip, **calendar and calendar_dates:** Indicate the service schedules.

Figure 1: Illustration of the GTFS Schema (scaled down version).

1.3 Related Works

In recent years, following the launch of ChatGPT, there is a growing literature of using LLMs in applications. In the intersection with the standardization domain though there are fewer works. It has been stated that LLMs can help automate the processing of unstructured data but still need expert programming and constant interaction (Qi and Wang (2024)) (Jiang et al. (2023)). In some studies the creation of a pipeline based on LLMs that can extract protocol information from unstructured natural language text and convert the data in the appropriate format so that they could be down streamed to other applications is explored (Jiang et al. (2023)), as well as ChatGPT's ability to understand and retrieve GTFS data , demonstrating promising results for query-based timetable retrieval (Devunuri et al. (2023)). In a more recent research, the concept of a generative AI-based framework was introduced, that leverages large language models to facilitate natural language interactions with General GTFS data by enabling users to query and interpret transit data through conversational interfaces without requiring technical knowledge of the GTFS format, demonstrating a promising application of LLMs in improving accessibility and usability of standardized mobility datasets (Devunuri, Lehe et al. (2024)). Our approach is focused on a specific domain, transport, but with a focus on extracting lessons that will be domain independent.

2. Methodology

In this section, we present our development activities in researching and creating software to automatically standardize transport datasets. We present the steps taken to:

- Collect and prepare appropriate data inputs.
- Use and adjust generative AI models to handle the standardization via a pipeline which extracts GTFS tables hierarchically.
- Implement an evaluation process using an LLM reasoning model, for measuring the accuracy of the generated GTFS tables.

For processing and preparation of the input data, we used the state-of-the-art gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 model from Google (Gemini 2.5 Pro Preview, 2025). The same model was used for extracting the GTFS tables along with Gemini 2.0 Flash (Gemini 2.0 Flash, n.d.) and OpenAI's GPT-4.1, GPT-4.1-mini and o4-mini models (GPT-4.1, 2025) (O4 mini, 2025). Gemini gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 is used again as a "judge" of how accurately each model executed that task during the evaluation of the generated GTFS data, because of its advanced reasoning capabilities.

2.1 Data Collection And Preprocessing

For developing and testing the pipeline, 50 images from transport schedules were collected manually. The images were selected to provide a comprehensive representation of a transport service, have wide variety and moderate resolutions. Languages were English and Greek. Images of the service embedded on a map regarding a service of transport mode (bus, rail, etc.) can commonly be found all around the world from printed travel guides to general information websites and many, mostly from public transport operators. Two examples are shown below.

Figure 2: Examples of unstructured transport schedules (Atlânticoline, n.d.) (Biosfera Express, n.d.).

2.2 Development Of The Pipeline

2.2.1 Transformation Of Raw Image To Text

The first step in the process of automating raw transport data to a standardized GTFS format is to extract all the information from the images that were collected during the previous section. A VLM model is tasked with extracting all text from the image, that is relevant to the image’s transport schedule information. Specifically, a thinking model with image input is used because of its advanced reasoning skills. The state-of-the-art reasoning and vision model Gemini 2.5 Pro Preview was selected for this task, trading higher inference cost for improved visual reasoning accuracy. A prompt as shown in the left figure below is enough to extract all the relevant information from an image in text form. The response of the model tasked with extracting the raw text from the image is also being presented in the right figure below. This step was validated manually to ensure that the VLM had perfect retainment on the information.

Figures 3,4: Image to Text instructions prompt and example of an extracted transport service data from an image in text form.

2.2.2 Converting Extracted Text To GTFS Tables

The next part in the pipeline includes the conversion of the extracted text from the raw image data, described in the previous section, to GTFS format. Most text inputs generated have a form similar to the one displayed in Figure 4. In this example, there is enough information to extract the GTFS **agency**, **routes**, **calendar**, **calendar_dates**, **trips**, **stops** and **stop_times** tables, at least partially. Because the GTFS tables have an inherent hierarchy (e.g., **trips** and **stops** table is required for filling **stop_times** table), the LLM model responsible for the conversion of raw text to GTFS data, is tasked to sequentially process and transform the free text input into the GTFS tables. Starting with the **agency** table, a smaller version of the prompt which extracts the relevant fields is presented below:

Figures 5,6: Prompt used to extract the agency table and model response in JSON format.

With the agency table extracted, the pipeline proceeds with the extraction of the table **routes**. Note how this requires information from the table agency, so that table is also provided in the prompt.

Figure 7,8: Prompt used to extract the routes table and output table in JSON format.

This process is repeated for each table in the order that their hierarchical structure demands that they are created. More specifically, the tables are generated in the following order: **agency, routes, calendar, calendar_dates, trips, stops, stop_times**. The example of this process that is displayed in the above figures demonstrates the ability of LLMs to extract the table's information. Note, for example, that the route_short_name field values "HORDA/MADALENA", "MADALENA/HORTA" directly corresponds to the names of the routes that are displayed in the raw extracted text figure. The model detected that and placed it in the proper field, which managed to identify after reading it in the documentation.

With analogous prompts for each one of the remaining tables, the extraction of all the GTFS data, described in section 1.2, is completed, even handling the **trips** and **stop_times** table which are at a second level in the hierarchy tree, which means that they each need to combine and incorporate information from previously extracted tables.

The following five models were selected and compared for generation of the tables at this step:

- **gpt-4.1**: state-of-the-art LLM model
- **o4-mini**: fast but highly intelligent reasoning model
- **gpt-4.1-mini**: lightweight LLM
- **gemini-2.0-flash**: extremely fast low-latency inference and cost-effective throughput
- **gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06**: state-of-the-art reasoning model

Each one of the models above produces a set of the seven GTFS tables that were mentioned earlier in this section. Consequently, each one of the generated sets of tables is later evaluated separately in order to quantify how well each model has executed the task of conversion of raw data to GTFS format.

2.3 Integration Of Human-In-The-Loop

The pipeline developed above for free text and images is very promising. However, given the inherent nature of generative AI models to hallucinate, the generated tables are not always correct or adhering to the GTFS standard precisely. For this reason, the integration of a human-in-the-loop (HIL) is crucial. Accordingly, another pipeline was developed, which gives a human GTFS expert the ability to:

- Guide the model by adjusting the prompts with custom instructions.
- Edit the extracted tables by altering the incorrect cells or adding more rows.
- Re-run the process at deeper hierarchy layers to avoid accumulation of errors.

2.4 Evaluation

To assess the quality of the automated GTFS conversion pipeline, a dedicated “judge” LLM is introduced, whose sole responsibility is to compare generated GTFS tables against both the source raw text that was extracted during the first step of the pipeline, and the official GTFS specification. Gemini 2.5 Pro Preview is implemented as judge during the evaluation, due to its superior reasoning capabilities, efficient handling of structured data, and proven accuracy in detecting subtle schema and content inconsistencies.

From each set of GTFS tables only the tables **trips**, **stops** and **stop_times** are evaluated, since these tables are considered the most difficult to construct due to foreign-key consistency requirements, errors tend to propagate downstream all the way to **stop_times table** and lastly, the images that were collected in this dataset often lacked **agency** and **routes** data, but always included some form of trips and stops schedules.

The evaluation proceeds in two stages:

1. For each one of the three generated GTFS files in each set under evaluation, an evaluation prompt is created to clearly instruct the judge model to verify schema compliance, internal consistency, and fidelity to the original text.
2. Subsequently, each prompt, along with the AI-generated GTFS output and the ground-truth raw text, is fed into the judge LLM as input. The model returns a structured JSON object containing:
 - **A quantitative overall score on a one to five scale**, describing the overall accuracy of the model based on the rubric defined in the prompt.
 - **A justification on the model’s reasoning** behind the score it assigned to the table, highlighting any discrepancies or errors.

For reference, the evaluation prompt and the output of the evaluation created for **stops** table can be viewed in the figures below:

Figures 9, 10: Prompt used for evaluation and response from “judge” model for generated stops table.

2.5 Results

The results of the evaluation for each of the 50 images are represented by the figures presented below. Figure 11 summarizes the score distributions (scaled from 1–5) for the three core GTFS tables, **trips**, **stops**, and **stop_times**, across five GTFS generation models (gemini-2.0-flash, gpt-4.1-mini, gpt-4.1, o4-mini, gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06). Figure 12 presents corresponding boxplots of these scores.

Figure 11: Histograms of scores given from each “judge” model per table.

Figure 12: Box plots of evaluation scores given from each “judge” model per table.

The validity of the results above can be further confirmed by the results presented on table 1. Table 1 represents the Mean±Standard Deviation of the scores of each model responsible for generating the corresponding GTFS table from raw data according to the judge model, showing which model has had the best average score, while simultaneously maintaining the minimum variability in the total of the scores it was assigned.

Table 1: Mean ± Standard Deviation of scores awarded to tables stops, trips, stop times by the judge model, for each GTFS generation model.

Mean± Standard Deviation	gemini- flash-2.0	gpt-4.1- mini	gpt-4.1	o4-mini	gemini-2.5-pro- preview-05-06
Stops	4.28±0.99	4.60±0.85	4.84±0.37	4.66±0.71	4.78±0.58
Trips	4.02±1.11	3.64±0.96	4.02±1.03	4.33±0.91	4.55±0.75
stop_times	2.76±0.90	2.90±1.08	2.92±1.30	3.57±1.16	3.96±0.96

In the evaluation of GTFS table generation performance across different language models, the results for the **stops** table, as illustrated in Figures 11 and 12, reveal consistently high performance across most models. Figure 11 shows a strong skew toward the highest score of 5.

For the **trips** table, the evaluation results in Figure 11 demonstrate a more balanced distribution of scores across the models, with gemini-2.5-pro-preview-05-06 and gpt-4.1 leading in terms of the number of perfect scores. The histogram shows slightly more variation than the stops table suggesting that while the overall performance is strong, the generated trips table exhibits more frequent deviations from perfect accuracy compared to the stops table.

The **stop_times** table presents the most challenging task for the models, as shown in both figures. Figure 11 reveals a more evenly distributed score profile, with no single model dominating the highest score category, while low scores, ranging from 1–3, appear more frequently for all models, even the strong reasoning models, suggesting recurrent issues with this table type. This indicates significant inconsistency in the quality of the generated stop_times tables, likely due to the table’s length, structural complexity and the denser relational dependencies that it entails.

2.6 Failure Modes

Large Language Models excel at pattern completion and natural-language understanding, but generating a perfect GTFS table from raw text runs into some fundamental challenges:

- The LLM’s **stops** table misapplies mandatory-field rules, expecting irrelevant columns (e.g., route_id, trip_id), over-enforcing stop_id uniqueness, and producing inconsistent stop_name formatting—indicating it lacks precise GTFS schema mapping and uniform naming conventions.
- The **trips** table oversimplifies service patterns by using wrong or single service_ids that ignore weekday/weekend/holiday differences, miscounts trips, misaligns coverage tolerances, and omits or invents departures. These flaws arise from its failure to translate nuanced schedule semantics and raw exceptions into precise GTFS entries.
- The **stop_times** table misapplies stop_id uniqueness, misaligns column lengths (dropping sequences or times), omits or halves trips/directions, scrambles stop_sequence order, leaves first/last times blank, and hallucinates or rounds times—reflecting the LLM’s failure to track records while remaining true to the original source, enforce ordering, and apply GTFS endpoint and bidirectional conventions.

3. Conclusions

This study systematically evaluated the ability of five large language models to generate the three core GTFS tables—**stops**, **trips**, and **stop_times**—from raw transit data. The findings of the implemented pipeline can be summarized as follows:

1. All evaluated models achieved high accuracy when generating the **stops** table. This indicates that even relatively “weaker” models can reliably extract simpler information.
2. Generation of the **trips** table proved somewhat more challenging: the overall spread of scores widened. This suggests that constructing coherent route sequences and timestamps exposes more subtle failure modes. Top tier models still deliver strong average performance.
3. The **stop_times** table, with its long, highly interdependent rows, was the most error-prone across all systems and no model achieved consistent top marks. This underlines the need for future work on handling dense tabular structures and mixed data types.
4. Overall, the approach is effective and the top tier model along with a human-in-the-loop to validate and correct the model’s responses, can generate GTFS tables much faster than a human expert would do alone.

3.1 Broader Impact

The automated standardization of transportation data using LLMs promises to unlock faster, more reliable applications. By converting heterogeneous sources, like scanned timetables, into standards with minimal human effort, transit agencies can publish up to date schedules more rapidly, enabling real time trip planners, accessibility tools, and on-demand mobility apps. Standardized, high quality data also feed directly into simulation models and performance dashboards, helping planners optimize network design, evaluate service changes, and assess equity impacts. The pipeline implemented in this research can also extend to other data standards, multimodal systems and use-cases.

3.2 Next Steps

Below an outline of targeted next-step research directions is presented, with the goal in mind being to overcome the core limitations of current LLM-based GTFS generation.

- **Improve the generation** of the **stop_times** table up to the point that it makes the whole pipeline reliable. One direction to explore is the iterative generation of **stop_times** per row of the trips table.
- **Improve the evaluation methodology** by 1. Creating a larger image dataset, 2. Improving the LLM-as-a-judge approach with more fine-grained scoring.
- **Improve the generations’ pipeline** in general by using prompts with more details, more information about the schedules, and edge-case handling instructions, especially as stronger reasoning models emerge.
- **Integrate additional transportation data sources**, such as transit maps and mobility datasets
- **Adjust the process to other data standards** like NeTeX and DaTeX II

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